

Sensitive determination of chromium by the catalytic hydrogen wave in the presence of thiocompounds at DME

N. Krishnaiah^a, A. Varaprasad^a, N. V. S. Naidu^{a*} and K. Saraswathi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati-517 502, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : nvsnaidu4@gmail.com

^bP.G. Department of Chemistry, P. B. Siddartha College of Arts & Sciences, Vijayawada-522 010, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract : A sensitive polarographic method for the determination of chromium is proposed, based on the catalytic hydrogen wave of Cr^{VI}-xanthate complexes in the presence of NH₄Cl at mercury electrode. The Cr^{VI}-xanthate complexes produce a catalytic hydrogen wave at -1.52 V vs SCE with potassium propyl xanthate (Kpxan) and at -1.47 V vs SCE with potassium cyclohexyl xanthate (Kchxan) in NH₄Cl-NH₄OH medium (pH 9.6 for Kpxan and 9.2 for Kchxan). The peak height is proportional to metal ion concentration. The proposed method is free of interference from other metal ions except Mo^{VI} and is evaluated to micro level Cr^{VI} down to 0.1 ppm by the determination of chromium content in drinking water samples, industrial effluents, tannery waste water and agricultural materials.

Keywords : Polarographic catalytic hydrogen wave, chromium(VI), xanthate, environmental samples.

Introduction

Catalytic hydrogen waves are due to the presence of certain catalytic substances in the solution, which contribute to the evolution of molecular hydrogen on the mercury electrode with simultaneous consumption of hydrogen ions. These waves are observed at less negative potentials than the usual waves of hydrogen discharge in the same solution. In addition to having considerable theoretical significance, the catalytic hydrogen wave is of great practical interest because it has a higher analytical sensitivity than other polarographic catalytic waves.

The catalytic hydrogen waves of organic thio compounds in the presence of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} at DME have been reported from our laboratories¹. An attempt has been made with potassium *n*-propyl xanthate (Kpxan) and potassium cyclohexyl xanthate (Kchxan) and found to give catalytic hydrogen currents in the potential range -1.52 and -1.47 V vs SCE with Cr^{VI} in NH₄Cl-NH₄OH medium at the pH 9.6 and 9.2 respectively. The quantitative experimental conditions have, therefore, been developed, the details of which are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

Reagents : All chemicals used are of analytical reagent grade unless specified otherwise. The solutions are

prepared in double distilled water and diluted to required strength. 5% NH₄OH and 1% HCl are used for pH adjustments. Gelatin and Triton X-100 are prepared and diluted as per requirement. Kpxan and Kchxan prepared and recrystallised according to standard procedures reported².

Water samples are preconcentrated by evaporation and standard addition method is used for analysis. Dry ash method³ is used for agricultural products for preparation of the sample solutions.

Apparatus : The equipment used is d.c. polarograph model CL-357 coupled with model LR-101 P strip chart recorder supplied by Elico Private Limited (Hyderabad, India). The pH measurements are made by using pH meter; model LI-120 (Elico Private Limited) with glass electrode of pH range 0-13. The temperature is maintained at 25 ± 0.2 °C and the flow of mercury at 2.5 s per drop.

Preparation of Cr^{VI} of real samples :

Drinking water samples : One liter of the samples collected from Kalyani Dam, Bore wells and Kapilatheertham water falls (Tirupati, Chittoor District, India) are preconcentrated to 100 ml.

Industrial effluents : One liter of the industrial efflu-

ents collected from Upper India Steel Limited and Pioneer Alloy Castings Limited, Gajulamandyam Industrial Estate, near Tirupati Town, Chittoor District, India and tannery waste water from SKS Industries Limited, Chrompet, Chennai, India are preconcentrated to 100 ml.

Agricultural material : 10 g of *Oryza sativa* sample (unpolished rice) and 5 g of piper betle (betle leaves) collected from Tirupati Town, Chittoor District are digested by dry ash method and brought into solution (10 g unpolished rice/25 ml and 5 g of betle leaves/500 ml triple distilled water).

Aliquots of the above solution are taken in a beaker and the quantitative experimental conditions are maintained as already mentioned in the Table 1. The precipitates of metal xanthates given by interfering metal ions are filtered off and the filtrate is polarographed after de-aeration. The results are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

The standard addition method is used for the analysis

Table 1. Quantitative experimental conditions for Cr^{VI} determination through catalytic hydrogen waves

Conditions	Kpxan	Kchxan
pH	9.6	9.2
NH ₄ Cl, M	0.4	0.4
Xanthate, mM	3.2	3.2
Chromium(VI), ppm	0.1-5.0	0.1-5.0

of chromium content in all the samples. These results are further supported by the values obtained using atomic absorption spectrophotometric method.

Results and discussion

The catalytic hydrogen waves of Cr^{VI} are recorded in neutral and alkaline media such as NH₄Cl-NH₄OH, KH₂PO₄, sodium tetraborate, HOAc-NaOAc, sodium citrate-HCl and tartaric acid-sodium tartarate supporting electrolytes containing xanthates as the ligands. The current of the catalytic hydrogen wave in NH₄Cl-NH₄OH supporting electrolyte is about twice than that in other reported media. 0.4 M NH₄Cl-NH₄OH supporting electrolyte is therefore selected for detailed study.

Effect of pH value : Keeping the concentration of metal ion (3.9 ppm) and xanthate (3.2 mM) constant in 0.4 M ammonium chloride, pH is varied from 6.5 to 10.0 adjusting with ammonium hydroxide. The heights of the catalytic wave increased with increase in pH up to 9.6 in case of Kpxan and 9.2 for Kchxan and decreased beyond these values. The peak potential is also shifted towards positive value with increase in pH. Therefore, pH 9.6 for Kpxan and 9.2 for Kchxan are fixed as quantitative parameters.

Effect of supporting electrolyte concentration : With an increase in the concentration of ammonium chloride

Table 2. Determination of chromium(VI) in water samples of Tirupati town

		(I) Kalyani Dam			(II) Bore well				
		Kpxan			Kchxan				
		NH ₄ Cl, M	Xanthate, mM	pH					
		: 0.4	: 3.2	: 9.6					
		Kpxan			Kchxan			AAS method	
Sample	Sl. no.	Cr ^{VI} Added (ppm)	Cr ^{VI} Found (ppm)	%Recovery	Cr ^{VI} Found (ppm)	%Recovery	Cr ^{VI} Found (ppm)	%Recovery	
I	1	0.80	0.80	100.00	0.80	100.00	0.80	100.00	
	2	1.00	0.98	98.00	1.00	100.00	0.98	98.00	
	3	1.20	1.20	100.00	1.18	98.33	1.20	100.00	
	4	1.40	1.38	98.57	1.38	98.59	1.40	100.00	
	5	1.50	1.50	100.00	1.50	100.00	1.49	99.33	
				Average	99.31%	Average	99.38%	Average	99.46%
II	1	0.80	0.80	100.00	0.80	100.00	0.80	100.00	
	2	1.00	0.98	98.00	0.98	98.00	0.98	98.00	
	3	1.20	1.19	99.16	1.19	99.16	1.20	100.00	
	4	1.40	1.38	98.57	1.40	100.00	1.38	98.57	
	5	1.50	1.50	100.00	1.48	98.66	1.49	99.33	
				Average	99.15%	Average	99.16%	Average	99.18%

Table 3

		(a) Kpxan		(b) Kchxan	
(I) Water samples					
(1) Kapilatheertham water falls - Tirupati town					
(II) Industrial effluents					
(1) Upper India Limited, Gajulamandiyam		} near Tirupati			
(2) Pioneer Alloy Castings Limited, Industrial Estate					
(3) S. K. S. Industries Limited, Chrompet, Chennai, India					
(III) Agricultural materials					
(1) Piper betle (betle leaves)					
		(a) Kpxan		(b) Kchxan	
NH ₄ Cl, M	:	0.4		0.4	
Xanthates, mM	:	3.2		3.2	
pH	:	9.6		9.2	
Sample ^{a/}		Cr ^{VI} (ppm)		Cr ^{VI} in the sample (ppm)	
xanthate		Added	Total	Catalytic	AAS
			found ^b	method	method
I	1	a	0.5	0.88	7.60
		b	0.5	0.87	7.40
					7.68
II	1	a	1.0	1.625	12.48
		b	1.0	1.625	12.50
	2	a	1.0	1.451	9.02
		b	1.0	1.451	9.20
					9.00
	3	a	0.5	1.982	148.20
		b	0.5	1.976	147.60
					150.00
III	1	a	0.5	1.786	1286.00
		b	0.5	1.790	1290.00
					1290.00

^a5 ml of the concentrated sample is used.

^bAverage of five individual determinations.

from 0.1 to 0.8 M at pH values selected above the height of the chromium(VI) wave is found to increase up to a certain value (0.4 M for both xanthates). With further increase in NH₄Cl the wave height decreased and therefore, 0.4 M NH₄Cl was maintained for further studies. The peak potential shifted towards positive potential with increase in NH₄Cl throughout the concentration range of NH₄Cl studied.

Effect of reagent concentration : The concentration of xanthates was varied from 0.6 to 4.0 mM keeping the metal ion at 3.9 ppm and ammonium chloride at 0.4 M at respective pH values selected earlier. For two xanthates the catalytic current peak height is maximum with xanthate concentration of 3.2 mM of both xanthates and independent beyond this concentration, indicating that the complexes got stabilized. The peak potential of the catalytic wave shifted towards more negative values on increasing the xanthate concentrations up to optimum con-

centrations 3.2 mM. The peak current is not of varied linearly with all concentrations of ligand which is a characteristic nature of catalytic waves.

Plot of {[Xan]/*i_p*} vs [Xan] is a straight line confirming the adsorption behaviour in the electrode reaction process.

The catalytic behavior of chromium-xanthate systems are further supported by the effect of mercury height on the peak current and temperature coefficient values. The catalytic current as well as *i_c*/√*h* decreased with the increase of the mercury column indicating that the current is catalytic in nature. The wave height increased with increase in temperature and temperature coefficient values decreased gradually from 15 to 30 °C.

The surfactant like gelatin suppresses the catalytic wave sharply up to 0.05% and by about 2% beyond and up to maximum permissible concentrations. The suppression with Triton X-100 is small when compared to gelatin. The peak potential shifted towards positive values.

The peak current increased linearly with Cr^{VI} concentration in the range 0.2 to 4.8 ppm in case of both xanthates. However, the sensitivity of the method is more with Kpxan compared to Kchxan because of strong complex of Cr^{VI} with Kpxan and therefore increased catalytic activity⁴.

The linear relationship between Cr^{VI} concentration and the catalytic current suggests that the method can be used successfully to determine trace amounts of Cr^{VI} in environmental samples, agriculture produce and alloys.

Most of the transition metal ions do not interfere with catalytic wave of Cr^{VI} under the conditions developed and Ni^{II} gets precipitated which can be removed by filtration. The only metal ion, Mo^{VI} interferes seriously by increasing the wave height of Cr^{VI}.

Anions such as carbonate and EDTA interfere by completely suppressing the chromium catalytic wave, where as nitrite and nitrate interfere as they also give catalytic current with Cr^{VI}.

Effect of indifferent cations : The effect of neutral salts on the chromium-xanthate systems is studied using lithium, sodium, potassium and calcium chlorides. With increase in concentration of chlorides the wave height decreased continuously and the decrease is less with sodium chloride to that of potassium chloride. The decrease in wave height is more for lithium chloride and much more for calcium chloride, indicating that Cr^{VI} xanthate complexes have adsorption properties on mercury electrode.

The peak potential is shifted towards less negative potentials with all cations of the neutral salts used.

Electrocapillary curves :

The presence of xanthates in NH_4Cl solution shifted the electrocapillary maximum to more negative value and the electrocapillary curve is suppressed on the positive side of the electrocapillary maximum, indicating that adsorption is involved in the reaction process (Fig. 1 for Kpxan).

Fig. 1. Electrocapillary curves.

Applications of the catalytic method : The developed method is applied to the analysis of trace quantities of chromium in drinking water samples, industrial effluents, tannery waste water and agricultural materials.

The results in Table 2 show that the drinking water drawn from bore wells and supplied to Tirupati town by Municipality from Kalyani Dam is free from chromium content. Though the water from the water falls of Kapilatheertham of Tirupati Town (Table 3, I) is found to have traces of chromium it is within the tolerance limits. Chromium(VI) detected from the industrial effluent (Table 3, II) indicates that the metal is present in trace levels and therefore, does not cause any hazards to the environment through the waste water that is discharged into public sewers. The chromium levels analyzed in agri-

cultural samples (Table 3, III) are in agreement with the reported values⁵. The results obtained using two ligands are in good agreement with atomic absorption spectrophotometric values.

Conclusions :

Chromium-xanthate complex is responsible for the generation of catalytic hydrogen waves. The linear dependence of the current on the pH and ligand concentration up to certain values are catalytic in nature. Effect of height of the mercury reservoir and temperature coefficient values are also indicative of catalytic nature of the complex. Further support of adsorption is indicated by the Langmuir adsorption isotherm curve, decrease of the height of the peak current with indifferent electrolytes and from the shape of the electrocapillary curve⁶ reinforces our observation. The method is selective without much interference except Mo^{VI} . The method is also sensitive with the detection limit up to 0.1 ppm, rapid and specific compared to diffusion current of Cr^{VI} in classical polarography.

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